

Article

Blockchain in Peer-to-Peer Platforms: Enhancing Sustainability and Customer Experience in Tourism

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Abstract: Blockchain technology is emerging as a high-impact solution for the tourism industry, a topic chosen for its growing research relevance and potential to revolutionise the tourism sector in several areas. This study examines how the combination of Blockchain technology and P2P platforms advances sustainability and marketing in the tourism accommodation market. It attempts to fill a gap in the literature by focusing on its application in two areas, namely digital markets and technology, which are expanding. The originality of this research lies in its comprehensive review of blockchain applications in tourism from a practical point of view, which has been largely unexplored in the existing literature. Through a bibliometric review of forty-two papers, various Blockchain applications were identified, such as improving transparency, trust, and efficiency in hotel operations and eliminating intermediaries to reduce costs. The adoption of smart contracts and the use of cryptocurrencies have also emerged as key trends. These findings highlight the transformative potential of Blockchain technology to build trust between hosts and guests, streamline processes, and improve the customer experience. However, they emphasise the need for the careful planning and consideration of the challenges associated with implementing this technology. Future research should further explore the specific applications of Blockchain technology in tourism to optimise its impact on industry and ensure long-term sustainability.

Keywords: blockchain technology; P2P platforms; tourist accommodation; marketing advancements; consumer adoption

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1. Introduction

1.1. Brief Overview of the Practical Application of Blockchain Technology in the Tourism Industry

Blockchain technology is often described as a decentralised ledger that utilises a consensus algorithm and immutable data structure to ensure the accuracy and transparency of transactions [1]. Since its introduction in 2008 [2], this technology has revolutionised the way data are stored and transmitted. It generates encrypted blocks of information, enabling secure and transparent storage and the transmission of transaction records [3]. Blockchains are known for their ability to facilitate cryptocurrency transfers and international payments and smart contract execution, thus eliminating the need for intermediaries. The usefulness of Blockchain technology has been demonstrated in various industries [4], including reducing financial costs and enhancing security and transparency. In the tourism industry, Blockchain technology plays a fundamental role in project financing, company management, and business model development [5,6], bringing benefits to the value chain [7,8].

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